

SBM_IND – SMART BUSINESS MODELS FOR INDUSTRY

“The network efficient use of flexibly deployable consumers will gain in importance in the future in order to react to the increased use of volatile renewables. The industry can play a central role if economically viable business models are created for them. That’s what we are working on in the Smart Business Models for Industry project.”

THOMAS KIENBERGER, Project Manager SBM_IND, Head of Chair of Energy Network Technology, Montanuniversität Leoben

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KEY FACTS

Duration: 09/18 – 08/20

Project volume: € 452,784

The Project Smart Business Models for Industry focuses on the development of business models designed to help both industrial companies as well as regional utilities in order to market their power plants flexibly and in a demand-based manner. Particular attention is paid to «network efficiency» to avoid expensive investments in energy networks by avoiding network overloads.

MAIN GOALS

Implementation of digital technologies and services to enhance grid stability through intelligent control of industry based electrical loads and storages.

Design and demonstration of innovative business process architectures especially suitable for small, local distribution system operators and their industrial customers.

Development of a Pre-Alpha-Software that allows using industrial flexibility options as needed by using an automated IT algorithm.

